

MAGNESIUM SUPPLEMENT AND MENTAL HEALTH DISORDERS: AN UPDATED REVIEW

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Abstract

Background: Magnesium ion (Mg^{2+}) is an important intracellular cation regulating neuronal excitability, neurotransmission, synaptic plasticity and stress response. Dysregulation in magnesium metabolism has been implicated in various neuropsychiatric disorders, however evidences remain inconsistent across the literature, limiting confirmation of its clinical utility.

Objectives: This review provides updated evidence on the therapeutic potential of magnesium in mental health disorders with emphasis on observational, interventional, experimental studies and randomized controlled trials as well as mechanistic insights, limitations and future research considerations.

Methodology: The methodology involved a comprehensive search of studies published between 1979-2025 (41 unique publications) across major scientific databases and repositories, to examine the relationship between magnesium homeostasis and mental health outcomes.

Results: Magnesium supplementation either alone or adjunct to pharmacological treatment, demonstrates therapeutic benefits, particularly in depression and anxiety. However, findings in schizophrenia, ADHD, autism and dementia remain inconsistent, largely due to heterogeneous study design, patient variability and inadequate randomized controlled trials.

Conclusion: Magnesium supplementation represents a promising, cost-effective and safe adjunct in the management of mental health disorders. However to establish its clinical relevance, well-designed, large-scale and randomized controlled trials, particularly those incorporating standardized formulations, outcome measures and mechanistic assessments are necessary.

Introduction:

Psychiatric disorders including depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder, schizophrenia, autism and sleep disorder affect over 1 billion people world-wide, accounting for 14% of the global population (1). Pharmacological therapeutic

options, though effective (2,3), often require long-term or even lifelong use, bringing adverse side effects (4,5).

In the recent years there has been growing interest in safe and cost-effective therapeutic

alternatives to conventional pharmacological interventions (6). Evidence suggests that micronutrient supplementation, particularly magnesium has shown promising results in several psychiatric conditions (7).

Magnesium is the fourth most abundant cation in the human body and the second most prevalent intracellular cation, participating in more than 600 enzyme-catalyzed reactions. Magnesium supports key processes in the body including, synaptic transmission, energy metabolism and membrane stability (8). In the central nervous system (CNS) it functions as a natural calcium antagonist, influencing neuronal excitability, intracellular signaling and synaptic plasticity (9).

Both observational and interventional studies have linked magnesium deficiency to neuropsychiatric disorders (10). Though findings are promising, inconsistencies persist, due to heterogeneous study designs, small sample size, patient characteristics, magnesium assessment methodology and supplementation protocols, complicate interpretation of magnesium's clinical utility.

This review systematically analysis the literature up to 2025, across major scientific databases focusing on the relationship between magnesium supplement and mental health outcomes, with emphasis on relevant studies, supplementation protocols and mechanistic insights.

Methodology:

A structured literature search was performed using PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science and Google Scholar for studies published up to 2025. Keywords included magnesium, depression, anxiety, schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, autism, ADHD, cognitive decline and sleep disorders. Both observational and interventional studies were considered, along with systematic reviews, randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and meta-analyses.

Inclusion criteria:

- i. magnesium status in relation to psychiatric or stress-related outcomes
- ii. Peer-reviewed clinical, epidemiological and experimental reports.
- iii. Publications in English language.

Exclusion criteria:

- Case reports without controls
- Conference abstracts lacking full data
- Studies with non-human outcomes unless directly providing mechanistic insight.

Magnesium status and supplementation across psychiatric and neurodevelopmental disorders

1. Depression:

Several large-scale epidemiological studies demonstrated an inverse relationship with dietary magnesium intake and risk of depression. Individuals with low dietary magnesium intake were prone to experience depression symptoms (5,11), supported by meta-analytical findings (12). Clinical evidence highlights magnesium deficient patients with major depressive disorder (MDD) compared to healthy controls (13).

Both interventional and randomized controlled trials (RCTs) studies support the findings, where magnesium supplementation improved depressive symptoms, with effects comparable to individuals receiving standard antidepressants (14). Meta-analytical studies also support the antidepressant potential of magnesium supplementation(15).

2. Anxiety:

Anxiety disorders show plausible link with magnesium deficiency, although clinical data is inconsistent (16). Clinical trials report mixed results, with some supporting anxiolytic effects of magnesium supplementation (17), while others fail to verify the findings (11). The inconsistency in the findings could most likely be due to difference in dosage formulations, dosage sizes, comorbidities and heterogeneous assessment tools. Studies showing positive anxiolytic effect of magnesium supplementation reducing anxiety in risk groups, including premenstrual women, older adults and individual exposed to stress risk (10).

3. Bipolar Disorder:

Several observational studies on bipolar disorder reported state-dependent response on serum magnesium levels, elevated during manic and reduced in depressive episodes (18). Therapeutically, magnesium supplementation in combination with mood stabilizers (lithium or

valproate) also showed mixed results. A small number of pilot trials involving bipolar patients, magnesium supplementation showed improved mood stabilization, sleep span and quality (19,20), while others found little consistent benefit (21).

4. Schizophrenia:

Altered magnesium metabolism has been implicated in schizophrenia pathophysiology. Observational studies and reviews report reduced serum magnesium in a subset of schizophrenia patients. Case-control studies has shown significantly lower serum magnesium concentrations in individuals with schizophrenia compared with healthy controls (9). Systematic reviews emphasize heterogeneity in findings, with some cohorts confirming magnesium deficiency, whereas others reported no significant association in schizophrenia (22). Clinical trials highlighted marginal improvements in psychiatric symptoms with adjunctive magnesium supplement (23).

5. Attention-Deficit-Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD):

Early observational and case-control studies identified significantly lower serum and erythrocyte magnesium levels in children with ADHD compared with healthy controls (24,25). Subsequent interventional studies and small scale clinical trials have further explored this relationship. Particularly when magnesium supplementation combined with vitamin B6, bring symptomatic improvements, such as attention span, impulsivity, and hyperkinetic behaviour (26). Cross-sectional studies confirmed magnesium deficiency in a subset of hyperactive children, suggesting a potential biological link (24). However, randomized controlled trials and systematic reviews produced mixed or no results in children supplemented with magnesium and vitamin B6 formulation (26,27).

6. Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD):

Autism spectrum disorder has also been linked to magnesium deficiency, particularly in children with behavioural disturbances, irritability and sensory processing abnormalities. Clinical trials on magnesium supplementation with vitamin B6 has been reported to improve social interaction and communication in autistic children

(Martineau). Subsequent small scale trials reinforce the findings, demonstrating partial improvements in hyperactivity, irritability, and repetitive behaviours among subsets of autistic children (26). RCTs and systematic reviews reported mixed outcomes, with some confirming improvements in repetitive behaviour and communication, while others found no significant effects (28,29,30,31)

7. Cognitive Decline and Neurodegenerative Disorders:

Magnesium plays a critical role in cognitive health and aging. Epidemiological studies suggest magnesium deficiency is associated with increased risk of mild cognitive impairment (MCI) and Alzheimer's (AD) disease (32). Animal models demonstrate, magnesium supplement reduces oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, amyloid- β deposition, while enhance synaptic plasticity and memory performance (33). Human pilot trials magnesium L-threonate supplementation, report modest memory and executive-function improvements in older adults (34). Recent systematic reviews suggest a possible U-shaped relationship between serum magnesium and dementia risk, with an optimal serum level around ~ 0.85 mmol/L (35).

8. Sleep Disorders and Stress-Related Conditions:

Clinical studies on magnesium supplementation in individuals with insomnia showed improved sleep parameters and reduced stress related symptoms. A small RCTs in older adults on magnesium oxide supplementation or other formulations report improved sleep onset, sleep quality and duration, reduced anxiety and muscle relaxation (36, 37). Stress physiology studies show that chronic stress increases urinary magnesium excretion, predisposing individuals to hypomagnesemia, irritability and fatigue. Subsequent magnesium supplementation has been shown to reduce stress-induced symptoms including, irritability and fatigue, suggesting potential for stress resilience enhancement (38).

Results

The available evidence through structured literature search highlighted clinical utility of magnesium in several psychiatric and cognitive

disorders, though the strength of evidence varies across different neuropsychiatric conditions.

Depression: Observational studies, RCTs and systematic reviews consistently link magnesium deficiency with depression and improvement upon dietary magnesium supplementation (MgCl₂ 248 mg/day) (39).

Anxiety and Stress: Clinical and observational findings on magnesium supplementation show mixed results. Perioperative and stress-exposed populations show anxiolytic benefit. RCTs show inconsistent results due to variations in magnesium formulations, dosage and assessment tools.

Bipolar Disorder and Schizophrenia: Emerging evidence links altered magnesium levels to bipolar disorder and schizophrenia. Magnesium supplementation may stabilize mood fluctuations and reduce extrapyramidal symptoms when given adjunctively with antipsychotics.

ADHD and Autism: Paediatric data show that magnesium deficiency is common among children with ADHD and autism. Some trials suggest symptom improvement with magnesium and vit B6 supplementation. Variability exists in

outcomes which may be reflect to differences in baseline magnesium status, genetic heterogeneity and concurrent interventions.

Cognitive Decline and Dementia: Observational studies demonstrate, both low and high serum magnesium levels are associated with increased risk of dementia. Preliminary RCTs with magnesium L-threonate show promising improvements in memory and executive functions.

Sleep Disorders: Small RCTs suggest that magnesium supplementation improves sleep latency, efficiency and subjective quality, particularly in older adults. Inconsistencies exist in the literature, limiting the generalizability and magnesium's clinical utility. Table 1 provides a consolidated overview, summarizing key findings on magnesium supplementation across major psychiatric and neurodevelopmental disorders, highlighting clinical implications, study design, proposed mechanisms, through representative clinical trial, RCTs, observational cohorts, meta-analyses and systematic reviews up to 2025.

Table 1. Summary on magnesium status and mental health disorders (Study type, mechanism, clinical implications and representative studies).

Disorder	Key Findings	Representative Studies	Mechanisms	Clinical Implications
Depression	Low dietary/serum Mg associated with risk; supplementation improves symptoms (PHQ-9). Meta-analyses confirm protective effect.	Tarleton & Littenberg (2017, RCT); Moabedi et al. (2023, meta-analysis); Hajhashemy et al. (2025, dose-response); Wang et al. (2018, cohort)	NMDA modulation, serotonin regulation, HPA axis stabilization	Mg may serve as adjunctive therapy in MDD. Larger multicenter RCTs needed.
Anxiety Disorders	Low Mg linked to heightened stress reactivity, GAD, panic; modest anxiolytic effects in some RCTs.	Boyle et al. (2017, review); Saba et al. (2022, RCT); Eby & Eby (2006, case series)	GABA enhancement, glutamate inhibition	Possible role in stress-related anxiety; requires standardized RCTs.
Bipolar Disorder	Serum Mg varies with mood state; small RCTs report mixed benefits with adjunct supplementation.	Siwek et al. (2015, case-control); Schefft et al. (2017, pilot trial); Rajizadeh et al. (2017, RCT)	NMDA receptor modulation, PKC signaling	Limited evidence; may aid mood stabilization and sleep regulation.
Schizophrenia	Reduced serum Mg reported; adjunctive Mg may reduce extrapyramidal side effects but not core symptoms.	Baj et al. (2020, review); Alexander et al. (1979, clinical trial)	NMDA hypofunction, dopamine regulation	Potential adjunct to antipsychotics, but evidence scarce.
ADHD	Low serum Mg common in children; Mg + B6 improves hyperactivity/attention in small trials.	Kozielec & Starobrat-Hermelin (1997, case-control); Mousain-Bosc et al. (2006, trial)	Catecholamine regulation, neuronal excitability	Promising adjunct in pediatric ADHD; larger blinded RCTs needed.
Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD)	Early trials suggested benefit of Mg + B6, but later studies showed inconsistent or no effects.	Martineau et al. (1985, trial); Tolbert et al. (1993, clinical); Nye & Brice (2005, review)	Neurotransmission stabilization, metabolic effects	Sometimes used as adjunct therapy; robust evidence lacking.
Cognitive Decline & Dementia	Low Mg intake linked to MCI/AD; Mg L-threonate improves cognition in animals and pilot human RCTs; possible U-shaped risk.	Barbagallo & Dominguez (2010, review); Slutsky et al. (2010, animal); Liao et al. (2024, pilot RCT); Chen et al. (2024, systematic review)	Oxidative stress reduction, synaptic plasticity, amyloid regulation	Neuroprotective potential; warrants larger clinical validation.
Sleep & Stress	Mg supplementation improves sleep latency, efficiency and subjective quality; stress increases urinary Mg loss.	Abbasi et al. (2012, RCT); Hausenblas et al. (2024, RCT); Pickering et al. (2020,observational)	GABA facilitation, HPA axis modulation	Supports role in sleep improvement and stress resilience.

PHQ-9 score: Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) scores by 6.0 points (95% CI: -7.9 to -4.2; P < 0.001) among adults with mild-to-moderate depressive symptoms. (248mg daily magnesium chloride supplementation for 6 weeks)

Discussion:

The evidence reviewed potential role of magnesium in the pathophysiology and management of mental health conditions. Mechanistic plausibility is strong, involving NMDA receptor modulation, serotonergic regulation and stabilization of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis. Collectively, the evidence supports magnesium supplementation as a potential adjunctive strategy, showing benefits in reducing depressive symptoms, improving sleep quality, enhancing cognitive function, and alleviating symptoms in neurodevelopmental conditions such as ADHD and autism spectrum disorder (ASD) (26)

Findings in anxiety and stress are more heterogeneous. Some RCTs and clinical observations suggest anxiolytic benefits, particularly in targeted subgroups such as premenstrual women, perioperative patients, and individuals under high stress. Mechanistically, these effects may be explained by magnesium's modulation of the GABAergic system, including enhancement of γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) neurotransmission and inhibition of excitatory glutamatergic activity (40, 41).

For bipolar disorder and schizophrenia, evidence remains preliminary and less conclusive. Mechanistically, magnesium is hypothesized to modulate intracellular signaling pathways, particularly via protein kinase C, and to act as an endogenous NMDA receptor blocker. However, insufficient sample sizes, heterogeneous supplementation strategies, and inconsistent methodologies limit the generalizability of these findings (42,43).

In neurodevelopmental disorders, particularly ADHD and ASD, associations with magnesium deficiency are consistently reported. Clinical studies combining magnesium with vitamin B6 supplementation indicate improvements in hyperactivity, attention, and certain behavioural outcomes. Nevertheless, methodological limitations, including small sample sizes and lack of adequate blinding, reduce confidence in these results.

Magnesium also shows promise in conditions linked to cognitive decline, aging, and sleep disturbances. In dementia, both low and high serum magnesium levels have been associated with

increased risk, suggesting a possible U-shaped relationship. Experimental studies and small-scale RCTs with magnesium L-threonate report improvements in memory, synaptic plasticity, and executive function, though large, well-designed trials are needed to validate these effects. In sleep disorders, magnesium supplementation has been shown to improve sleep latency, efficiency, and subjective quality. Mechanistically, these benefits are likely mediated through NMDA receptor regulation, serotonergic pathways, GABAergic neurotransmission, and stabilization of the HPA axis (36,37, 44)

Overall, the literature highlights the broad physiological role of magnesium in brain function and psychiatric health. While the most consistent evidence supports its therapeutic role in depression, emerging but less definitive evidence exists for anxiety, bipolar disorder, schizophrenia, ADHD, ASD, dementia, and sleep disorders.

Conclusion

Magnesium is an essential cation with broad physiological functions in mental health disorders. The most consistent evidence supports in depression, where both clinical and observational evidence suggest a protective and therapeutic effect. Evidence for anxiety, bipolar disorder, schizophrenia, ADHD, autism, cognitive decline and sleep disturbances is supportive but less conclusive. Taken together, the literature emphasizes magnesium's potential therapeutic role as a safe, cost-effective adjunctive strategy in psychiatric care. Despite encouraging signals, many trials remain limited by small sample sizes, heterogeneous methodologies, and inconsistent outcome measures. These findings underscore both the breadth of evidence, linking magnesium with psychiatric outcomes and the critical need for larger, well-designed mechanistic trials. Future research should focus on well-powered RCTs that consider baseline magnesium status, dose-response relationships and comparative efficacy of different formulations. Such evidence will clarify magnesium's role as a patient-specific adjunct in psychiatric care.

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